

Characteristics of teaching practices in Rural Education: analysis of actions related to teacher training and experience report of pedagogical methodologies proposals for the teaching of specific content

 Renan Mota Silva¹

¹ Universidade Federal do Pará - UFPA. Instituto de Filosofia e Ciências Humanas. Rua Augusto Corrêa, 01. Guamá. Belém - PA. Brasil.

Author for correspondence: renanmota16@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT. Rural Education-RE involves specific elements that are representative of the way of living in the countryside. In a brief search for references related to teacher education focused on CE and also examples of proposals for content teaching, an apparent lack of studies on these themes was identified. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to identify characteristics related to the training of teachers for CE and, in addition, to present practical examples of pedagogical methodologies for teaching specific subjects. For this, a bibliographic research was carried out in scientific articles as well as in a specific database and search engine. The results confirmed, for both themes, the gaps in the scientific literature. The articles found, in general, predominantly involve the analysis of teacher education in the North and Northeast regions. As for the proposals for pedagogical teaching methodologies, the themes are almost exclusively related to science, biology and sustainability. In conclusion, there is an understanding that other curricular components, such as Portuguese language, mathematics and others, have been neglected, either because of their understanding of their lesser relevance in relation to the subjects or contents mentioned, or because researchers are not producing research in this context.

Keywords: rural education, alternation pedagogy, teacher training, pedagogical methodologies.

Características das práticas de ensino na Educação do Campo: análise de ações relacionadas à formação de professores e relato de experiências de propostas de metodologias pedagógicas para o ensino de conteúdos específicos

RESUMO. A Educação do Campo-EC envolve elementos próprios que são representativos do modo de viver no campo. Em uma breve busca de referências relacionadas com a formação docente voltada à EC e também exemplos de propostas para o ensino de conteúdos, foi identificada uma aparente escassez de estudo acerca dessas temáticas. Diante disso, os objetivos deste estudo foram a identificação de características relacionadas à formação de professores para a EC e, além disso, apresentar exemplos práticos de metodologias pedagógicas para o ensino de assuntos específicos. Para isso, foi realizada uma pesquisa bibliográfica em artigos científicos bem como em base de dados e buscador específico. Os resultados confirmaram, para ambos os temas, as lacunas existentes na literatura científica. Os artigos encontrados, em geral, envolvem de modo predominante na análise da formação docente as regiões norte e nordeste. Já quanto as propostas de metodologias pedagógicas de ensino, os temas quase que exclusivamente, estão relacionados com ciências, biologia e sustentabilidade. Concluindo, há o entendimento de que outros componentes curriculares, tais como a língua portuguesa, matemática e outros, têm sido negligenciados, seja pelo entendimento de sua menor relevância em relação às disciplinas ou conteúdos citados, ou porque os pesquisadores não estejam produzindo pesquisas nesse contexto.

Palavras-chave: educação do campo, pedagogia da alternância, formação de professores, metodologias pedagógicas.

Características de las prácticas docentes en Educación Rural: análisis de acciones relacionadas con la formación docente e informe de experiencia de propuestas de metodologías pedagógicas para la enseñanza de contenidos específicos

RESUMEN. La Educación Rural-ER involucra elementos específicos que son representativos de la forma de vida en el campo. En una breve búsqueda de referencias relacionadas con la formación del profesorado centradas en la EC y también ejemplos de propuestas para la enseñanza de contenidos, se identificó una aparente falta de estudios sobre estos temas. Por tanto, los objetivos de este estudio fueron identificar características relacionadas con la formación de docentes para EC y, además, presentar ejemplos prácticos de metodologías pedagógicas para la enseñanza de materias específicas. Para ello, se realizó una búsqueda bibliográfica de artículos científicos, también en la base de datos y en un buscador específico. Los resultados confirmaron, para ambos temas, la brecha en la literatura científica. Los artículos encontrados, en general, involucran predominantemente el análisis de la formación docente en las regiones Norte y Nordeste. En cuanto a las propuestas de metodologías pedagógicas de enseñanza, los temas están casi exclusivamente relacionados con la ciencia, la biología y la sostenibilidad. En conclusión, se entiende que se han descuidado otras componentes curriculares, como lengua portuguesa, matemáticas y otros, ya sea por entender su menor relevancia en relación con las materias o contenidos mencionados, bien porque los investigadores no están produciendo investigación en este contexto.

Palabras clave: educación rural, pedagogía de alternancia, formación docente, metodologías pedagógicas.

Introduction

According to Almeida, Barcelos, and Gomes (2021) Rural Education (RE) in Brazil is, at the same time, a demand and a result of the political fight of the people who live, who develop their work, and who claim for the land. Among them are *quilombolas*ⁱ, riverine people, forest peoples, peasants, landless people, indigenous people, and others, who have developed their actions in response to extreme inequality in the distribution of land.

Rural social movements have been claiming the right to an education that addresses their socio-historical demands. Such movements understand that Rural Education constitutes an important instrument for understanding the political, economic, social, and environmental relations that cross the peasant territory (Andrade, Nogueira & Neves, 2019, p. 4, author's translation).

Furthermore, Cavalcanti, and Carvalho (2021) describe that RE encompasses its own elements that are representative of the way of living in the countryside. The authors corroborate the information described in the previous paragraph by stating that such elements "... range from the struggles of rural workers in social movements to public policies aimed at rural schools." (Cavalcanti & Carvalho, 2021, p. 4, author's translation).

This claim is very similar to the one made by a group of French farmers who were dissatisfied with their educational system, which for them did not meet specificities related to education aimed at rural areas. They emphasized that there was a demand for the school's education offered to young people to meet their social particularities, enabling, in addition to professionalization in agricultural activities, also elements for the social and economic development of their region (Teixeira, Bernartt & Trindade, 2008, author's translation).

This dissatisfaction culminated in 1935 with the emergence of a movement called Pedagogy of Alternation (PA) (Estevam, 2003; Magalhães, 2004). Then, an organization of teaching emerges precisely in the form of alternating times when young men (young people) remained at school or in spaces equivalent to it and times when they remained on family property. This Pedagogy of Alternation, according to Teixeira, Bernartt, and Trindade (2008) is of great importance so that there is a connection between moments of doing in socio-professional life and moments of school activities themselves, using the knowledge that was accumulated by the young person through their experiences concrete experiences.

Overmore, Andrade, Nogueira, and Neves (2019, p. 4) pointed out about:

...the construction of Rural Education takes place in a space of struggles and political clashes of social movements, in defense of an education that has a political and pedagogical plan that can meet the specificities of rural subjects.

In this corpus of understanding, Silva (2021, p. 43) emphasizes that “the land issues and the difficulties and lack of education in the countryside, add up in the same direction as the requirements of differentiated education...”. It still reaffirms that: “Without a doubt, it adds in the sense of dimensioning the universe of people who are waiting for an opportunity to access this education”. Arroyo (2011) helps us to substantiate this issue with his reflection on the proposal to incorporate rural education, demonstrating in his definition the importance of considering issues about land, territory, culture and the identity of rural peoples.

By mentioning that among these specificities, the Pedagogy of Alternation acts precisely in the sense of disarticulating colonial educational practices responsible for uprooting both identities and territories, making it possible to consider it as a decolonial practice. Among the reasons for this is the fact that:

Assuming that labor as an educative principle, the Pedagogy of Alternation allows young people from the countryside the possibility of continuing their studies and having access to scientific and technological knowledge not as something given by others, but as knowledge conquered and constructed from the problematization of their reality, which involves research, the researcher's distanced look at his daily life (Cordeiro, Reis & Hage, 2011, p. 116, author's translation).

Concerning decolonial education, it is understood that:

The presence of racial discrimination and prejudice is still very strong in our society, as a result of the processes of oppression and domination from northern countries to subaltern countries and groups. These characteristics are presented mainly by the social inequality that dares to persist to the present day in Latin American countries and not least in the various regions of Brazil. In the case of our country, the significant evolution in the improvement that is observed, unfortunately, figures more prominently in the legislation. It seeks to ensure an education for ethnic-racial relations, to value the history and culture of indigenous and African peoples. However, in the day-to-day practicality in classrooms, the observed result is different: it is seen that these seals of Laws do not have the expected effect: an egalitarian and emancipatory education (Silva, 2021, p. 90, author's translation).

The present article was conceived from the moment when it was found, when evaluating the productions related to Rural Education, a theme that the author focuses on daily to elucidate, that they, in general, were grouped into two themes:

- Studies with a historical context of the RE and the Pedagogy of Alternation, which invariably passed through their legal, legal, or regulatory aspects by competent bodies or instances; and

• The scarcity of studies, in principle, that addressed two other themes in which interest was aroused: a) the characteristics of teacher training to work in Rural Education; and b) experiences that present practical examples and their results the proposals of pedagogical methodologies for teaching specific contents.

For this reason, the objectives of this article were, firstly:

a) present up-to-date information on how teacher training has taken place in courses specifically in Rural Education or in undergraduate courses with subjects in which RE is addressed; and

b) present practical examples of pedagogical proposals and their analysis by their proponents regarding their benefits in teaching content and in facilitating or optimizing teachingⁱⁱ and learningⁱⁱⁱ.

The justification for this research is that the compilation of findings regarding the training of teachers and teaching and learning practices involving Rural Education may allow the reproduction of those that have proved to be more effective or beneficial. It will also be possible, from the identification of particularities of the region in which the study was developed or the theme that was worked on, that adaptations or adjustments are implemented, making it possible to replicate its proposals in the reality in which the reader works.

Methodological aspects of research

This investigation consists in a qualitative literature review. According to Prestes (2012), this type of study is characterized by being theoretical concerning its objective, explanatory concerning the form of study, and also bibliographic regarding the object of study.

In this sense, theoretical research involves an analysis only of the theory related to the chosen theme, that is, there is no practical analysis *in loco* of what is investigated nor any type of intervention to evaluate its effects. Explanatory research, on the other hand, is conducted from the recording, analysis, and interpretation of data, even theoretical, in search of clarification of a particular theme or problem. Finally, in the bibliographic research, there is a search for answers from previously produced references. For this, there is a need to have methodological procedures to guarantee the quality of these references and, consequently, of their research.

For the results section, built under the name “Teacher Training for Rural Education and Experience Reports of Proposals for Pedagogical Teaching Methodologies”, only scientific

articles published in the last 05 (five) years (2017-2021) were included, counting the year of production of the present work, written in Portuguese, quantitative, qualitative, or review, and with full and free access to the text.

It should be noted that articles not related to the objectives of this work were excluded, as well as productions not characterized as scientific articles, that is, abstracts, expanded abstracts, monographs, dissertations, and theses.

The Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) database and the CAPES/MEC Journal Portal were verified as search sources. The bases were selected according to their scientific rigor so that a journal can be indexed. Additionally, the Google Scholar search engine was also used and, in this case, Qualis CAPES was used to verify the quality of the journal in which the article was published.

In all these search locations, combined descriptors were used, which theoretically would return works related to the objectives. They were:

a) “countryside education AND alternation pedagogy”; and b) “teaching practices AND rural education AND alternation pedagogy”.

The selection of articles took place in two stages. In the first one, the title and abstract were read to understand the article's proposal and if it would contribute to achieving the objectives of this work. In the second, a full reading of the article was carried.

Teacher Training for CE and Experience Reports of Proposals for Pedagogical Teaching Methodologies

The results for this section will be presented in two ways.

The first will initially be in the form of a table, in which I a summary of the main information regarding both identification and content of the articles found will be presented and, in particular, in greater detail, the results and conclusions obtained (Table 1). Next, in a descriptive way, these works are discussed, comparing and comparing them. In this part, the works will be related to the training of teachers in Rural Education.

In the second part, which is only descriptive, several studies are presented that specifically addressed the proposal of pedagogical methodologies of different contents, always in the context of Rural Education. These works, as a rule, will be works in which there was a practical application of a teaching methodology with an analysis of its results from the perspective of the authors.

Table 1 – Summary table of the articles studied.

Title	Author(s)	Journal/Year	Aim	Metodology	Results	Conclusions
<i>1) Field education in the training of teachers of the Pedagogy course at the Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA) – Campus Imperatriz.</i>	Silva, I. R., Campos, I. M. C., & Zapparoli, W. G.	Pedagógica Journal, 2021.	- To analyze the curriculum of the Pedagogy course of the Center for Social Sciences, Health and Technology (CCSST) of the Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Campus Imperatriz.	- Bibliographic review and document analysis of the Pedagogical Project of the Course and the teaching plan of the Rural Education subject.	- The Rural Education subject is optional, which makes it have low attendance or choice for being attended. - There are other subjects in the course, these are mandatory, which also address the theme or related contents, but in a limited way. - These last-mentioned subjects allow contact and discussion of the topic, in addition to understanding its importance for the plural context in which educators are inserted.	- There is a need for debate about the offer of Rural Education in the form of an elective subject. - The curriculum opens the way for training that respects the different contexts in which professionals can work, for this reason, it is very important that specificities are contemplated in a pedagogical project of any course, including that of pedagogy.
<i>2) Teaching practices in rural education: teaching experience in the training of undergraduates at the State University of Alagoas (UNEAL).</i>	Santos, S. S.	Diversitas Journal, 2020a.	- Present the proposal of teaching practices and how they are carried out in the EC discipline. - How it constitutes an important contribution to the training of undergraduates in the Portuguese-French Pedagogy and Letters courses at the State University of Alagoas (UNEAL).	- Observation of contexts in which Rural Education is offered at the State University of Alagoas (UNEAL) and the legislation in statewide and federal spheres.	- Insertion of the Rural Education discipline in undergraduate courses after completion of the course (graduation) with the same name. - Organization of the discipline based on the identification of demands from social movements in the countryside. - Classes are taught through discussion and reflection on various topics.	- Teaching in Rural Education must have an inclusive look. - It must be understood that Rural Education has a dynamic, political, and critical character, is necessary to see the local reality, and that the content to be taught considers this reality. - This discipline requires specific knowledge from the professor, political commitment, research in the area, and dialogue outside the university.

(continuation) – Summary table of the articles studied.

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study of official documents that regulate and regulate Rural Education. -Field visit to a 3rd-year school (elementary school) located in a settlement coordinated by the Landless Rural Workers Movement (MST). - During this visit, there was a class on medicinal plants. - The rooms are multigrade with a strong focus on literacy. - Classes aimed not only at the contents proposed by the education department but also at training new militants. - In a meeting with leaders, the reality and struggles of that community were known. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural Education has specific difficulties, especially in that state sphere. - The training of new teachers must integrate the knowledge studied, produced, analyzed, and evaluated with the experience in the schools themselves, trying in the medium to long term, breaking the vicious cycle of insufficient qualification, inadequate and distant from the peasant reality.
3) <i>Internationalization of research and production of knowledge on education in the field of education in the northeast region (2013-2020).</i>	Santos, A. R.	Práxis Educational Journal,2020b.	To map the scientific production and the internationalization of research in the post Graduate course on Rural Education in the northeast region of Brazil.	State of the art from the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) database between 2013 and 2020.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence of growing research on Rural Education. - This increase is due to the increase in the number of courses, programs, and research groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Due to the findings identified in the works found, there is difficulty in internationalizing research and in the social insertion of researchers in Rural Education.

Table 1 (continuation) – Summary table of the articles studied.

Source:

					- There is a lack of investment by funding agencies for research projects in the field of Rural Education	- The little that has already occurred is mainly due to the militancy of researchers linked to social movements.
4) <i>Systematization of experiences: an analysis of the internship of experiences as a pedagogical tool at the Escola Família Agrícola Santa Cruz do Sul</i>	Ávila, J. S., Borges, B. C., & Moretti, C. Z.	Young Searches Journal, 2020.	- Understand the importance of the experienced internship as a pedagogical tool for the "do-distance" to occur in the alternation between school-time and family-owned time.	Analysis of internship experience through monitoring of preparation and pedagogical coordination seminars at Escola Família Agrícola de Santa Cruz do Sul (EFASC)	- It was possible to better understand the alternating educational process of this school and the importance of this instrument for the construction of new knowledge. - Identification of the importance of autonomy and dialogue for the exchange of knowledge and different techniques used by families in the countryside. - Differences in the reports and reflections of the internship experience between women and men students, both in the tasks performed on the family property and in the forms of socialization with the families.	- Identification of a dynamic between gender relations and their character of social reproduction that makes do-knowledge even more complex.

Author's elaboration (2022).

In the first study presented, that of Silva, Campos, and Zaparoli (2021), there is a similarity with the work of Santos (2020) because both contemplate the reality of the same region of the country, the northeast region. However, the similarities do not go beyond this aspect.

In the case of Santos (2020), it is initially contextualized as a fact that gave rise to the degree courses at the State University of Alagoas and which is quite common in the history of the implantations or creations of public universities in Brazil, that is, the beginning by the courses of degree to contribute to the training of teachers to work, especially in the interior of the States.

At UNEAL, the creation of a degree course in Rural Education was no different. It emerged not only as a strategic need, from an educational and economic point of view, but at the same time “as a counter-hegemonic project that goes against the grain of agricultural policies developed in the last 10 (ten) years.” (Santos, 2020, p. 2209). Also according to the author, in that region, the scenario historically found is that of large estates, the exploitation of sugarcane, and the ethnic constitution of the presence of blacks and indigenous people colonized by white Europeans.

Rural education, from this perspective, emerges as one of those collective and action activities that involve expectations, and commitments and shows the reality of injustices against rural men and women. These subjects challenge the state, the legitimate representative of the interests of the bourgeoisie. The collectively organized marches can serve as tools for training and political pressure, with public acts, involving educators, students, children, and the elderly in the dissemination of the struggle for land and education. (Ramofly, 2013, p. 4, author's translation).

This is another characteristic, now of the Rural Education courses or subjects with the same name taught in licentiates. It is an education aimed at people who practice subsistence agriculture on small properties, often organized in the form of cooperatives. It is another look at land use, completely different from large producers, even involved in export strategies.

The course at that institution also has a close relationship with actions or organizations related to rural workers, such as the Permanent State Forum for Rural Education (FEPEC) and the Contextualized Education Network of the Wild (Agreste) and Semi-Arid Region (RECASA). Both have served as support and discussion space for both educators and peasant workers.

All these characteristics are quite different from the way RE is approached in another public university, also in the Northeast, the Federal University of Maranhão. It, as shown in

Table 1, there is no specific discipline of Rural Education offered on a mandatory basis. This is somewhat surprising because although they are institutions from different states, it is clear that their reality is very similar concerning disputes over land between social movements or even small producers and family agriculture with the large landowners. Proof of this is that news of serious confrontations between them is not rare, which often results in death.

Because of this, Silva, Campos, and Zamparoli (2021) pointed out that some approaches are necessary to understand the importance of offering Rural Education as a compulsory subject. According to the authors, there is currently a movement to affirm the public policy of Rural Education in Brazilian universities, and this unfeasibility on the part of the pedagogy course at the Federal University of Maranhão of the mandatory nature of the discipline makes it difficult for academics to understand the need of a fundamental public policy to meet the interests of the rural people, something that represents a clear reality of the state of Maranhão.

To close this discussion, which is more specific about the northeast region, there is the study by Santos (2020b). From it, an interesting literature review was produced to understand the profile of productions related to Rural Education exactly in this region, it was possible to verify that although it represents a place with ample need for adequate training of licensed professionals, research is still incipient.

Another study, now related to another region of the country, more precisely in Santa Cruz do Sul, in the Rio Grande do Sul (RS), focuses on the agricultural school, using the Escola Família Agrícola de Santa Cruz do Sul (EFASC), was founded in 2009, as a reference. The article brings interesting information that demonstrates the importance of Rural Education. For example, in the 10 years of operation of the aforementioned school, 254 young people were trained, of which 89% still have some kind of work relationship on the land.

Figure 1 - Number of young people (last 10 years) graduating from Escola Família Agrícola de Santa Cruz do Sul.

Source: Production of researcher (2022).

In addition to this link being related to family farming, with training and acting as agricultural technicians, many of them also started to work as educators or are attending undergraduate or graduate courses in related areas (Ávila, Borges & Moretti, 2020).

The authors add that in the 50 years of existence of the Pedagogy of Alternation in this country, the understanding has prevailed that this method values family participation and coexistence in a boarding school, alternating between different spaces and educational times where education takes place. It thus represents a methodology in which teaching is organized taking advantage of alternating formative experiences throughout different spaces and times, aiming at professional training.

From this perspective, still, to achieve the objective of this study, after presenting general aspects of Rural Education in different regions of the country, reports of experiences will now be reported only in a descriptive way, that is, in the body of the text. of teaching practices to serve as a reference for other educators to implement similar proposals. When presented by the authors, positive (facilitating) and negative (limiting) points identified by them will also be indicated.

An aspect that should be mentioned here is the limitation of studies found regarding the variability of the journals in which they are published. When research was carried out either in the databases or in the search engines used, although of excellent quality, the works were restricted to a single scientific journal.

The first of them is by Piancastelli et al. (2021). For the authors, RE lacks methodologies that are consonant with its theoretical-epistemological paradigms. According to them, few studies that result in educational products aimed at the field itself are produced. In fact, in this research, as already mentioned and it is possible to observe so far, there are great limitations in productions of this type.

In the case of Piancastelli et al. (2021), a game proposal for a pedagogical game was presented in which parasitology could be worked on more attractively and efficiently, since the teaching of this topic in basic education, according to them, is restricted to providing knowledge of the pathogen, vector, host, and presentation. Of disease cycles and how it is possible to prevent it. All these subjects are dealt with traditionally, without any connection with the social context in which this information is transmitted.

From this bias, the topic addressed in the article was Chagas' disease and the proposed game was called *Barbeiragem*. The authors pointed out that the aforementioned trypanosomiasis was chosen because of its still very expressive numbers and because,

according to the World Health Organization (WHO), it is a neglected tropical disease. In the region of Minas Gerais, it is still considered hyperendemic and with high morbidity and mortality. Twenty-two students from the Degree in Rural Education, with an emphasis on Life and Nature Sciences, from the Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG) participated in the proposed activity.

The results found by the researchers revealed a good acceptance of the game, verified from the positive opinions that were registered. For them, there is the expectation that the proposed activity can, with playful characteristics and carried out outside the classroom, assist in the training of teachers and serve as a didactic resource for use in the communities in which they will work.

In another study, the central theme was science teaching (Melo, Batista & Camargo, 2021). The research was carried out in a rural school located in a traditional community in a municipality in Amazonas (AM) and the objective was to discuss in what proportion the combination of traditional and popular knowledge about plants contributes to the development of scientific education of students of a riverside school in the south of Amazonas. Fifteen students from the 7th, 8th and 9th grades of Elementary School participated and the investigation took place through questions, practical classes and drawings.

The authors found the existence of a wealth of information about plants in the knowledge already existing in the students' lives. They also highlighted the importance of articulating this knowledge or lived experience in combination with scientific knowledge for teaching and learning in Natural Sciences.

Such findings reinforce an aspect widely discussed in this article and found in the various works with the theme Rural Education, that is, the importance of not neglecting the knowledge acquired by those who throughout their lives have learned or acquired practical and direct information from the field. field, but contextualizing or adapting them to what is being taught at a given moment. The premise of a unique knowledge as valid, of an educator, teacher, teacher holding it and a student, student receiving and not questioning received information has been unacceptable for a long time.

The next article was produced "Purely traditional education" by Mora, Gomes and Barbado (2021) aimed to characterize a state rural school located in a district of Paraná (PR) regarding environmental education and sustainability. The research was carried out through documentary research, environmental perception and focus group analysis.

The authors identified notable points linked to the sustainability tripod. In terms of the environment, there was a lack of actions aimed at environmental education, in addition to a few correct environmental practices. Regarding the social aspect, there was a lack of feeling of belonging in the school community, a precarious appreciation of the teaching and learning process and an abandoned vegetable garden. In the economic aspect, they observed financial difficulties in the families.

Regarding the teaching of Natural Sciences, in general, the importance of discussing the integration of knowledge in Rural Education based on methodologies that consider the social, cultural, and environmental knowledge of students was highlighted.

Final considerations

The first objective of this paper was to present information related to the training of teachers and teachers focused on Rural Education. A first conclusion is that there is a tendency that RE disciplines when they are not mandatory in undergraduate courses are not selected to be taken. From this finding, the researchers suggested that they be part of the list of mandatory subjects to be taken. For this, the pedagogical project of a course must be reformulated.

This discipline must invariably be planned and executed considering the existence of experiences carried out *in loco* in rural schools and communities related to it. The idea is that the teaching and learning process does not distance itself from the peasant reality.

Regarding research on this topic, there is a great scarcity of research and scientific productions that result from them. At least in part, the reason for this has been attributed to an equal lack of funding from research agencies, as courses, research groups, and postgraduate programs in Rural Education have increased significantly in number, but their scientific productions have not increased at the same time.

The second objective of this article was to elucidate examples of proposals for pedagogical methodologies of specific content in rural schools. Findings showed that again there is a very important shortage of productions in this context. The hypothesis is that it would be possible to find activities carried out in practice in rural schools that could be replicated in reality and in the reader's place of action. However, the few references found addressed activities related to science and biology. Themes such as sustainability and some diseases that specifically affect rural people are those that are almost exclusively found.

Although unquestionably relevant, it is also essential that subjects such as Portuguese and Mathematics are contemplated due to their importance in the inclusion of the public that is part of Rural Education in society in general, whether for social, cultural, or even economic reasons.

In this way, it is recommended that researchers and research groups that work in the field of Education in the Countryside invest in projects that evaluate in practice how the teaching and learning process has taken place and whether the results have been in line with what is desired or recommended in the RE.

References

Almeida, S. F., Barcelos, D. C., & Gomes, D. R. (2021). Educação do campo como expressão do legado de Paulo Freire: educar para a liberdade na licenciatura por meio da Pedagogia da Alternância e do Projeto de Estudo Temático. *Práxis Educativa*, 16, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.5212/PraxEduc.v.16.16624.016>

Andrade, F. M. R., Nogueira, L. P. M., & Neves, L. C. (2019). Educação do Campo em giro decolonial: a experiência do Tempo Comunidade na Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF). *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, 4, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e7178>

Ávila, J. S., Borges, B. C., & Moretti, C. Z. (2020). Sistematização de experiências: uma análise do estágio de vivências como instrumento pedagógico na escola família agrícola de Santa Cruz do Sul. *Revista Jovens Pesquisadores*, 10(1), 1-16.

Arroyo, M. G. (2011). *Currículo, território em disputa*. Petrópolis, RJ: Vozes.

Cavalcanti, A. P. H., & Carvalho, W. L. (2021). O atendimento escolar em classes multisseriadas no município de Buenos Aires: representação de docentes à luz da política e educação do campo. *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, 6, 1-26.

Cordeiro, G. N. K., Reis, N. S., & Hage, S. M. (2011). *Pedagogia da Alternância e seus desafios para assegurar a formação humana dos sujeitos e a sustentabilidade do campo*. Em *Aberto*, 24(85), 115-125.

Estevam, D. O. (2003). *Casa familiar rural: a Casa Familiar Rural formação com base na Pedagogia da Alternância* (Dissertação de Mestrado). Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis.

Magalhães, M. S. (2004). *Escola Família Agrícola: uma escola em movimento* (Dissertação de Mestrado). Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo, Vitória.

Melo, P. R. H., Batista, E. R. M., & Camargo, T. S. (2021). Educação do campo e o ensino de ciências: experiências em uma escola ribeirinha no Sul do Estado do Amazonas. *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, 6, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e6994>

Mora, E. P., Gomes, P. P., & Barbado, N. (2021). Educação ambiental e sustentabilidade: estudo de caso na Escola Estadual do Campo Padre Antônio Vieira – ensino fundamental, Francisco Alves/PR. *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, 6, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e10817>

Piancastelli, A. M., Araújo, B. G., Mota, J. Q., & Vianey, J. P. (2021). A formação inicial de professores e a educação do campo: uma proposta de jogo para o ensino da parasitologia. *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, 6, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e7058>

Prestes, M. L. M. (2012). *A pesquisa e a construção do conhecimento científico: do planejamento aos textos, da escola à academia*. Catanduva: Respel.

Ramofly, B. S. (2013). Educação do campo, movimentos sociais e ensino de história. In *XXVII Simpósio de História*. Natal, RN, 2013.

Sacristán, J. G., & Gómez, A. I. P. (2007). *Compreender e transformar o ensino*. 4.^a edição. Porto Alegre: Artmed.

Santos, S. G. (2020a). Práticas de ensino na educação do campo: experiência docente na formação de licenciandos da Universidade Estadual de Alagoas. *Diversitas Journal*, 5(3), 2106-2216. <https://doi.org/10.17648/diversitas-journal-v5i3-1213>

Santos, A. R. (2020b). Internacionalização da pesquisa e produção do conhecimento sobre educação do campo da área da educação na região Nordeste (2013-2020). *Revista Práxis Educacional*, 16(43), 196-228.

Silva, I. R., Campos, I. M. C., & Zapparoli, W. G. (2021). Educação do campo na formação de professores do curso de pedagogia da UFMA – Campus Imperatriz. *Revista Pedagógica*, 23, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.22196/rp.v22i0.5400>

Silva, R. M. (2021). *Comunidade Quilombola da Ilha da Marambaia/RJ: Educação, Ancestralidade e Decolonialidade* (Dissertação de Mestrado). Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro.

Teixeira, E. S., Bernartt, M. L., & Trindade, G. A. (2008). Estudos sobre Pedagogia da Alternância no Brasil: revisão de literatura e perspectivas para a pesquisa. *Educação e Pesquisa*, 34(2), 227-242. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1517-97022008000200002>

ⁱ Legal category used by the Brazilian State since the promulgation of the Federal Constitution of 1988, aiming to ensure definitive property ownership to rural black communities with their own historical trajectory and specific territorial relations, as well as black ancestry related to the slavery period (Silva, 2021, author's translation).

ⁱⁱ In the perception of teaching as a practical activity that promotes educational exchanges to guide in a certain direction the influences that are exerted on the new generations (Sacristán & Gómez, 2007, p. 81, author's translation).

ⁱⁱⁱ Learning understood as a process of giving meaning and meaning to the situations in which the individual finds himself. Under the observable manifestations, processes of discernment and intentional pursuit of goals and targets develop (Sacristán & Gómez, 2007, p. 33, author's translation).

Article Information

Received on January 06th, 2021
Accepted on September 03th, 2021
Published on October, 29th, 2022

Author Contributions: The author was responsible for the designing, delineating, analyzing and interpreting the data, production of the manuscript, critical revision of the content and approval of the final version published.

Conflict of Interest: None reported.

Article Peer Review

Double review.

Funding

No funding.

How to cite this article

APA

Silva, R. M. (2022). Characteristics of teaching practices in Rural Education: analysis of actions related to teacher training and experience report of pedagogical methodologies proposals for the teaching of specific content. *Rev. Bras. Educ. Camp.*, 7, e13712. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e13712>

ABNT

SILVA, R. M. Characteristics of teaching practices in Rural Education: analysis of actions related to teacher training and experience report of pedagogical methodologies proposals for the teaching of specific content. **Rev. Bras. Educ. Camp.**, Tocantinópolis, v. 7, e13712, 2022. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20873/uft.rbec.e13712>